

Analytical Comparison of Impedance and Optical Platelet Counting in the Presence of Platelet Mimickers in Hematology Analysers

Husna Dilshana. K

Assistant Professor, Palakkad Institute of Medical Science

ABSTRACT

Accurate and precise platelet counting is essential in disease monitoring and treatment, and it is a vital research tool for standardizing counts within whole blood, platelet rich plasma or purified platelet preparation. It is said that with development of two-dimensional analysis using light scatter or fluorescence, limitations with one-dimensional analysis like impedance method, are reduced. This study is about evaluating significance of effects on platelet counting in presence of common platelet confounders by comparing two methods, impedance and optical, in the same analyzer.

OBJECTIVE: To compare the two methods of platelet counting, impedance and optical, in automated hematology analyzer, in presence of platelet confounders.

MATERIAL AND METHODS: A retrospective analytical study was conducted over a period of two months. Platelet count of patients with microcytosis, and thrombocytopenia were compared against the platelet count of the controls with normal blood picture and results were analyzed.

RESULTS: One hundred and forty patients with microcytosis and one fifty-seven with thrombocytopenia were compared with controls. Platelet count was higher in 48% of patients by optical method and only 2% by impedance method in control subjects. Presence of microcytosis resulted in higher platelet count by impedance method 18%. Thrombocytopenia resulted in exaggeration of this phenomenon with 31% of platelet count showing higher values. There was no correlation between platelet count (optical method) and difference between platelet count by two methods.

CONCLUSION: Presence of microcytosis and thrombocytopenia results in significant increase in platelet count by impedance method.

NOVELTY: Platelet count by impedance method in presence of confounder is directly compared with counts by optical method and controls.

KEYWORDS: Platelet count, Impedance method, optical method, Thrombocytopenia, Microcytosis

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I. INTRODUCTION

Platelet is the smallest blood cell measuring between 1-3 μm in diameter or with a cell volume of 2-20 fl. and appears as dark purple spots on a stained blood smear. Platelets indicate the number of platelets in a person with normal range of about 150,000-450,000 platelets in each microliter of blood.

Platelets are small anucleate cell fragments adapted to adhere to damaged blood vessels, aggregate on one another and facilitate the generation of thrombin and play important role in hemostasis. Platelet counts are routinely performed by modern automated blood cell analyzers. Accurate and precise platelet counting is essential in disease monitoring

and treatment, and it is a vital research tool for standardizing counts within whole blood, platelet rich plasma or purified platelet preparation.

Assessment of platelet count is essential as numerical deficiency or defect in their function may lead to bleeding. In severely thrombocytopenic patients, the platelet count is important as count is used to determine whether the patient requires platelet transfusion. Finding a reliable method to enumerate low platelet counts remains a challenge.

Manual phase contrast microscopy method was developed in 1953. (Brecher, Schneiderman & Cronkite, 1953). In this method, platelets can be easily discriminated against lysed

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red cells in hemocytometer. In early impedance analyzers, platelet counting could only be performed by analysis of platelet rich plasma (PRP) or purified platelet preparations and was thus prone to considerable error. PLT-M counting method performed in the chamber of the Neubauer hemacytometer has been recommended by many laboratories as the reference method, but it is time consuming, complicated, and operator dependent. (9)

The introduction of impedance method in platelet counting improved the precision of results, but it has many limitations. Increasing demand for reducing the frequency of platelet transfusions has resulted in a general fall in the prophylactic threshold. However, clinicians must also understand the limitations associated with platelet counting for them to be confident at this threshold of platelet count.

There are various problems with platelet count accuracy and precision which include the following: (1) instrument technologies failing to eliminate cellular and particulate interference; (2) unsatisfactory reproducibility of manual platelet counting methods; and (3) preanalytical interference, such as platelet clumping.

Currently there are two methods optical density and electrical impedance methods employed by automated hematology analyzers. Impedance platelet count uses hydrodynamic focusing and single dimensional histogram to count platelets. Optical counting method can differentiate platelets according to type and strength of light signals.

Measurement of platelet counts using automated analyzers is usually quite precise and accurate. However, accuracy of the automated platelet counts can be compromised when measuring very low platelet counts or in the presence of interference from non-platelet particles such as microcytic RBC, fragmented RBC, Giant RBCs or cell debris.

Microcytosis defines the presence of numerous microcytic red blood cells with its mean corpuscular volume (MCV) less than 80 fl. Blood samples which usually drawn from patients with thalassemia, iron deficiency anemia, hemolytic autoimmune anemia, and malignant neoplasm contains lot of fragmented and microcytic red blood cells which interferes with the platelet counts.

If the red blood cells in the sample have burst or hemolysed, its fragments will be falsely counted as platelets. This will consequently increase the number of platelets and produces anomalous result. It is important to overcome this problem to avoid unnecessary treatment and platelet transfusion.

Impedance method is unable to distinguish platelets from particles whose size and volume are similar to platelets. These limitations related to inability of automated analyzers to discriminate lead to the development of immunological methods using flow cytometry technology. International Council for Standardization in Hematology and the International Society for Laboratory Hematology in 2001 recommended the use of labeled PLTs and fluorescence

flow cytometry. However, the high cost of this method limits its routine use.

As microcytosis can lead to inaccurate platelet counting by automated analyzers, determining true platelet counts is necessary to minimize counting errors, especially in thalassemia, iron deficiency anemia as both conditions are associated with low MCV.

II. METHODS

I. Study design and study setting: A retrospective analytical study was conducted over a period of two months in Department of Pathology, JSS Hospital, Mysore

II. Source of data and study population: Platelet count of patients with microcytosis, and thrombocytopenia were compared against the platelet count of the controls with normal blood picture and results were analyzed with the data collected from Laboratory Information system.

III Sample size and Randomization: A study with sample size 398 subjects were conducted with control samples having normal blood counts and blood picture, test samples being patients with Thrombocytopenia (Platelet count < 150000/cumm) and those with reduced MCV (Less than 70 fl) of RBCs. 101 subjects are taken as controls, 140 subjects with microcytosis and 157 subjects with thrombocytopenia from 1st June 2021 to 31st August 2021 are taken as samples. The hematological parameters like MCV, RBC, RDW, IPF, HCT are collected from Laboratory information system of the hospital and analyzed between two methods. Random numbers are generated in Microsoft excel and analyzed with Excel Ver 4.3.

III. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

101 subjects were taken as controls, 140 subjects with microcytosis and 157 subjects with thrombocytopenia from 1st June 2021 to 31st August 2021. All the quantitative data were summarized as mean with standard deviation or median with interquartile range and categorical data expressed as proportions. Correlation of the continuous variables was reported as Pearson correlation coefficient(r). Agreement between two continuous variables which measured the same parameters was done using Bland – Altman analysis. A difference of > +/- 5% between two methods is considered clinically significant.

Informed consents were obtained from the patients or bystanders after describing the details of the study by means of printed informed consent form and Ethical committee clearance was obtained before beginning the study.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We studied 101 subjects as controls and 140 subjects with microcytosis and 157 subjects with thrombocytopenia.

Table 1: Intermethod variability between optical and impedance platelet counts in control, microcytosis and thrombocytopenia groups

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Baseline characteristics			
Parameter - Median (IQR)	Sample Category		
	Control	Microcytosis	Thrombocytopenia
Age (yrs)	44 (30 - 55.7)	40.5 (28 - 55)	48.5 (31.8 - 62.1)
Hemoglobin (gm/dl)	13.7 (12.7 - 15.1)	9.3 (7.4 - 10.6)	11.3 (9.09 - 13.4)
MCV (fl)	85.7 (82.9 - 88.6)	63 (58.9 - 67)	85.3 (80.4 - 92.2)
RBC count (millions/cumm)	4.65 (4.34 - 5.09)	4.75 (4.06 - 5.18)	3.76 (2.87 - 4.57)
RDW	13.2 (12.8 - 13.7)	18.3 (16.9 - 20.2)	14.5 (13.4 - 16)
Platelet count - Optical (Lakhs/cumm)	2.84 (2.39 - 3.34)	3.36 (2.58 - 4.3)	1.01 (0.62 - 1.28)
IPF (%)	2.5 (1.6 - 3.5)	4.2 (2.8 - 6.3)	6.6 (3.73 - 11.38)
Gender M%/F%	50.5 / 49.5	40.8 / 59.2	63.9 / 36.1

	P Opt Higher (>5%)	P Opt and P Imp +/- 5%	P Imp higher (>5%)
Control	48%	50%	2%
Microcytosis	25%	57%	18%
Thrombocytopenia	22%	47%	31%

Controls

No of subjects = 101

Minimum platelet count by optimal method = 1.53

Maximum platelet count by optical method = 4.42

Minimum platelet count by impedance method = 1.37

Maximum platelet count by impedance method = 4.23

Bland Altman analysis agreement = 95% of the platelet count values obtained by imp method lie between 13000 less to 31000 more than counts obtained by optical method

Correlation (r) between platelet count by optical method and the difference between the counts by two methods was 4.6% with a coefficient of determination of 46%. The coefficient variation between two methods exceeded by 5% in 33.7% of the cases.

Microcytosis

No of subjects = 140

Minimum platelet count by optical method = 1.51

Maximum platelet count by optical method = 7.57

Minimum platelet count by impedance method = 1.49

Maximum platelet count by impedance method = 7.42

Bland Altman analysis agreement = 95% of the platelet count values obtained by imp method lies between 71000 less to 23500 more than counts obtained by optical method

Correlation (r) between platelet count by optical method and the difference between the counts by two methods was 13.8% with a coefficient of determination of 3.6%. The coefficient of variation between two methods exceeded by 5% in 24.3% of cases.

Thrombocytopenia

No of subjects = 157

Minimum platelet count by optical method = 0.04

Maximum platelet count by optical method = 1.48

Minimum platelet count by impedance method = 0.07

Maximum platelet count by impedance method = 1.69

Bland Altman analysis agreement = 95% of the platelet count values obtained by impedance method lie between

17100 less to 13300 more than counts obtained by optical method

Correlation (r) between platelet count by optical method and the difference between the counts by two methods was 28.3% with a coefficient of determination of 0.6%. The coefficient variation between two methods exceeded by 5% in 41.8% of the cases.

Over the years, platelet counting has been performed by microscopic counting, automated blood cell analyzers and international reference method based on flow cytometry. Currently there are two methods, optical density and electrical impedance methods employed by automated hematology analyzers. (2). Impedance method is a classic platelet counting method invented by Beckman Coulter.(2). Impedance platelet count uses hydrodynamic focusing and single dimensional histogram to count platelets. Optical counting method can differentiate platelets according to type and strength of light signals (1).

Electrical Impedance method is based on the particle size .In this method, machine is unable to distinguish platelets from particles the size and volume of which are like platelets (platelet mimickers).Platelet Mimickers are Microcytes (RBC with low MCV) in conditions like Thalassemia and Iron deficiency anemia and excessive lipid particles in the serum as in Post prandial state and in Nephrotic syndrome. As microcytosis can lead to inaccurate platelet counting by automated analyzers, determining true platelet counts is necessary to minimize counting errors, especially in thalassemia, iron deficiency anemia as both conditions is associated with low MCV. Potential consequences of this methodological bias are that degree of thrombocytopenia may be underrecognized, or thrombocytopenia may be overlooked in such patients.

There remains a debate regarding which method is more suitable for platelet counting, especially in platelet interference like in microcytosis and in thrombocytopenia. This study found that optical method yielded a higher platelet count compared to impedance method in 101 controls, whereas impedance method yielded a higher count in microcytosis and in thrombocytopenia. Impedance method overestimated platelet counts in samples with MCV<70 fl in the current study. It may be because of small size of RBC which will be counted as platelet by the impedance method, giving a false high count, potentially affecting platelet transfusion decisions for patients.

In EDTA samples, platelets are in tiny clumps. So, when it passes through the optical chamber, these will get lysed. This can be taken as the explanation for the higher platelet count in optical method.

In thrombocytopenia, there is peripheral destruction of platelets and megakaryocytes produce immature forms - giant platelets by the bone marrow. Giant platelets whose size are similar to RBC are counted as RBC and give spurious low platelet count usually by impedance method.

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But in this study, in thrombocytopenia, there is increase in platelet count by impedance method.

Thrombocytopenia cannot be considered as a major confounding factor, since giant platelets will not be significant except in severe thrombocytopenia or giant platelet syndrome and microcytes are going to confound the platelets. So, impedance method resulted in higher platelet count.

Most of the cases of thrombocytopenia which are infection associated will have associated fragmented RBCs which will be counted as platelet by impedance method. This also explains the higher value of impedance method compared to optical method in thrombocytopenia.

According to Bland Altman Analysis agreement, 95% of platelet values obtained by impedance method lies between 13000 less to 31000 more than counts obtained by optical method. By Bland Altman analysis agreement, there is drastic difference in platelet values obtained by two methods of platelet counting even in the controls. Coefficient variation between two methods exceeded by 5 % in 33.7% of the controls. In microcytosis and thrombocytopenia, the correlation in platelet values obtained by impedance and optical method become even more wide indicating no correlation in platelet values between two methods.

Our results showed that the impedance method overestimated the platelet counts. These findings are in agreement with those reported by other groups. [7,8] Cid et al., showed that impedance method provided higher platelet counts when compared to the optical or immunological methods and also failed to give platelet measurements in the lower thrombocytopenic range.

According to Mohammed et al, impedance method significantly overestimated platelet counts in microcytic and thrombocytopenic blood samples. And optical method is found to be superior to impedance method in estimating platelet counts in samples with low MCV. (1).

These findings suggest that the impedance method will not provide the most accurate platelet counts at low MCV values and may instead yield a false-high count, potentially affecting platelet transfusion decisions for patients. These results are in line with those from a study by Ninama et al., who reported that the impedance method was not always reliable for assessing platelet counts in cases of severe microcytosis after comparing platelet counts obtained by the impedance method on the CELL-DYN™ 3700 (Abbott Laboratories) analyzer with those obtained from a manual technique with ammonium oxalate.11 Similarly, Pan et al. showed that the impedance method overestimated platelet counts in microcytic samples using the XE 2100™ automated analyzer (Sysmex Corp).(1)

A previous study that compared the accuracy of PLT counting between the impedance and optical methods using 3 different automated analyzers concluded that the precision of impedance methods was better than the precision of

optical methods. The difference in their findings and ours may highlight the impact of sample selection on the accuracy of PLT counts. We suggest that patient population, sample selection, and reference method should be considered possible explanations for discordant results of evaluations of platelet count methods.

Since this is a retrospective study, we could not examine the peripheral smear to check for the giant platelets. If it had been prospective study, peripheral smear can be examined of all the patients, it could have been more authentic. Then platelet aggregates, thrombocyte abnormalities or white cell or red cell fragments interfering with the platelet counts could have been assessed more precisely. This becomes a major limitation of this study.

Figure 1: Percentage difference between optical and impedance platelet counts in control group

Figure 2: Percentage difference between optical and impedance platelet counts in microcytic anemia

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FIGURE 3. PERCENTAGE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN OPTICAL AND IMPEDANCE COUNTS IN THROMBOCYTOPENIA

CONCLUSIONS

Presence of microcytosis and thrombocytopenia results in significant increase in platelet count by impedance method. As a result, physicians should keep in mind that the impedance method may significantly overestimate platelet count in microcytosis with thrombocytopenia, which may affect transfusion decisions.

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REFERENCES

- I. Boulassel MR, Al-Farsi R, Al-Hashmi S, Al-Riyami H, Khan H, Al-Kindi S. Accuracy of platelet counting by optical and impedance methods in patients with thrombocytopenia and microcytosis. *Sultan Qaboos University medical journal*. 2015 Nov;15(4): e463.
- II. Sun Y, Hu Z, Huang Z, Chen H, Qin S, Jianing Z, Chen S, Qin X, Ye Y, Wang C. Compare the accuracy and precision of Coulter LH780, Mindray BC-6000 Plus, and Sysmex XN-9000 with the international reference flow cytometric method in platelet counting. *Plos one*. 2019 May 24;14(5): e0217298.
- III. Kottke-Marchant K, Davis B, editors. *Laboratory hematology practice*. John Wiley & Sons; 2012 Jun 6.
- IV. Segal HC, Briggs C, Kunka S, Casbard A, Harrison P, Machin SJ, Murphy MF. Accuracy of platelet counting haematology analyzers in severe thrombocytopenia and potential impact on platelet transfusion. *British journal of haematology*. 2005 Feb;128(4):520-5
- V. Mohamed-Rachid B, Raya AF, Sulaiman AH, Salam AK. Comparative analysis of four methods for enumeration of platelet counts in thrombocytopenic patients. *Journal of Applied Hematology*. 2015 Jul 1;6(3):119.
- VI. Briggs C, Harrison P, Machin SJ. Continuing developments with the automated platelet count 1. *International journal of laboratory hematology*. 2007 Apr;29(2):77-91.
- VII. Harrison P, Horton A, Grant D, Briggs C, Machin S. Immunoplatelet counting: a proposed new reference procedure. *British journal of haematology*. 2000 Feb 1;108(2):228-35.
- VIII. Sandhaus LM, Osei ES, Agrawal NN, Dillman CA, Meyerson HJ. Platelet counting by the coulter LH 750, sysmex XE 2100, and advia 120: a comparative analysis using the RBC/platelet ratio reference method. *American journal of clinical pathology*. 2002 Aug 1;118(2):235-41.
- IX. Bavani S, Elysha NI, Reezal I. Influence of Red Cell Microcytosis in the Accuracy of Platelet Counting by Automated Methods. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*. 2019 Apr 1;11(4):1506-9.
- X. Pan LL, Chen CM, Huang WT, Sun CK. Enhanced accuracy of optical platelet counts in microcytic anemia. *Laboratory Medicine*. 2014 Feb 1;45(1):32-6.
- XI. Kim BR, Choi JL, Kim JE, Woo KS, Kim KH, Kim JM, Kim SH, Han JY. Evaluation of Platelet count by the CELL-DYN Sapphire CD61 Immunoplatelet Method in Patients with Hematologic Diseases Receiving Chemotherapy. *Laboratory Medicine Online*. 2015 Jul 1;5(3):133-6.